

Bioinformatics training needs of the Australian life science community: 2023/24 survey

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Introduction

The life sciences are a dynamic, data-centric field requiring life-long learning to build transferable digital research and bioinformatics skills.

Australian BioCommons and the National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative provide short-format training in bioinformatics to the Australian life science community. To ensure the relevance of our program of training, we regularly survey the life science community to find out what they need to learn to progress their work and how they prefer to learn. Past surveys have revealed the variety of topics that are in demand and highlighted changing attitudes to online learning (see EMBL-ABR's 2016 survey¹ and our 2021² survey).

The way we work has changed again since our last survey in late 2021³. Many are returning to the office and in person activities, and new bioinformatics methods are gaining in popularity (e.g. spatial omics, AI/machine learning). We repeated our training needs survey in late 2023 to explore changes in the preferred format of training and in the topics to be covered.

We recognise the 146 responses to the survey is a small snapshot of the needs of an estimated 30,000 members⁴ of the Australian life science community. It is intended to complement other engagement and gap analysis strategies and as a starting point for deeper analysis and exploration of bioinformatics training needs.

We share these results in the spirit of openness and in the hope that it will spark conversations about the bioinformatics training needs of the life science community locally, nationally and internationally.

Methodology

Survey design and distribution

The 2023/24 survey was developed by the Australian BioCommons and the National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative and is modelled on our 2021 survey (see supplementary materials for the full set of questions).

The survey was designed with the intention of answering two key questions:

- What format of training is preferred?
- What topics need to be covered?

In the 2023/24 survey we changed how we asked about topics people require training on, from a checklist of options to a free text response. Respondents could list up to ten topics that they needed to learn in response to the prompt “I need to learn now to...”. This change was made to improve specificity of the answers and to allow us to capture a greater variety of needs by encouraging self-reflection. We also introduced the use of [Field of Research classification codes](#).

The survey was administered online using Survey Monkey and was open for responses between December 2023 and March 2024. It was distributed to life science communities via a number of channels including:

- Australian BioCommons and National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative social media accounts
- Australian BioCommons and partner newsletters
- National communities of practice and forums
- Australian BioCommons workshops and webinars

Data analysis and data availability

Data curation, analysis and plotting of graphs and charts was performed using Google Sheets. Postcode data was plotted using GoogleMaps. WordClouds were generated using WordArt.com and Excalidraw was used to illustrate groupings of training topics.

Free text responses were lightly curated to aid interpretation and identification of themes. Specifically:

- State/territory is inferred from the postcode provided by respondents using openly available mappings^{5,6}.
- Similar responses to free text questions for example 'None', 'NONE' and 'none' were consolidated.
- For the creation of Word clouds, some words were combined into commonly used phrases e.g. "single cell", "PhD Student".
- Organisation names were curated for consistent spelling and results are shown at the organisation level (e.g. Diamantina Institute University of Queensland is shown as 'University of Queensland').
- Responses where dual appointments are indicated are counted under both organisations e.g. Garvan, UNSW = Garvan AND UNSW.

We identified themes within the free text answers to the question "I need to learn how to..." based on word clouds, manual categorisation informed by the [EDAM ontology](#)⁷ and our professional experience, and suggestions from SparkAI (The University of Melbourne's custom AI using Anthropic Claude 3 Sonnet (200k)). We manually combined and refined these themes by performing three rounds of review and categorisation.

In the final, fourth round, each response was assigned one or more high level topics:

- Data analysis, management and visualisation
- Programming and computational skills
- Other

And, where possible, assigned one or more:

- Domain/topic (e.g. Cloud computing, Proteomics)
- Application, tool or type of data (e.g. RNAseq, Nextflow)

The final classification of all responses is provided as a supplementary file.

Results and observations

Who responded to the survey?

The survey received 145 responses from across Australia and one international response which was excluded from all subsequent analyses (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A. Map of responses by postcode (an [interactive version of this map](#) is available) and **B.** The number of survey responses by state/territory.

The majority of responses are from people in the early-mid career stage (97.3%) including PhD students, Postdoctoral researchers, and those in bioinformatics/biostatistics roles (Figure 2 A and C). They have a mixed level of bioinformatics skills with most (68.5%) considering themselves in the beginner-intermediate category (Figure 2 B). They are affiliated with 56 different organisations (see the supplementary files for a breakdown of responses by organisation), with the majority from Academic/Research based organisations (Figure 2 D) and work across a variety of fields of research including environmental, agricultural and health sciences (Figure 2 E).

Figure 2: **A** The career stage of respondents **B**. Self-reported level of competency in bioinformatics and computational biology. **C**. Word cloud of job titles provided by respondents ([view an interactive version here](#)). **D**. Sector in which respondents work or study where one or more option could be selected. **E**. The field of research in which respondents work or study where one or more option could be selected.

Access to training

Most respondents are past-participants of training offered by one or more members of the National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative (Figure 3). They are also gaining training from sources including EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), Intersect, Software and Data Carpentry, Coursera, DataCamp, ABACBS and universities and research institutes.

Sources of training

Figure 3: Number of respondents accessing training offered by the National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative members. Multiple options could be selected.

As in our 2021 survey, most are not confident or are unsure if their training needs will be met by their local institution (Figure 4). Although the survey did not explore the reasons for these responses, it is likely that awareness and availability of training are contributing factors. This emphasises the need for ongoing engagement with the research community to highlight training opportunities and the continued importance of national and international collaborations to bring specialised training to a wider audience.

Confidence in training needs being met by local institution

Figure 4: Confidence that training needs will be met by local institutions.

Preferred modes of training delivery

Almost everyone (144/145 respondents) chose more than one mode of training delivery. Online and in-person instructor-led hands-on workshops continue to be a popular formats of training but self-paced online learning, and working through vignettes had a similar level of interest (Figure 5).

Further analysis suggests that respondents desire a combination of instructor-led and self-paced learning with one respondent specifically commenting that this is their preferred way to learn. Around half of the people choosing one of the instructor-led options also chose self-paced online learning (70/132 respondents) and almost all who chose vignettes (81/98 respondents) or online learning (70/83 respondents) also chose instructor-led options.

Mode of training

Figure 5: Preferred modes of training. Multiple options could be selected.

The preferred session length is a half day/ 3-4 hours and there was no clear preference for the number of sessions or their spacing (Figure 6).

Figure 6: A. Preferred length of training events. **B.** Preferred frequency of training events. Multiple options could be selected.

What topics do they need to learn about?

All respondents expressed an interest in learning two or more of the tools or platforms from the list provided in the survey. Other tools/platforms mentioned by respondents included Rust, Golang, SQL, Jupyter, QIIME2, and SIMCA. (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Desired training by tool or platform. Respondents could select multiple options.

When asked to self-define what they need to learn to advance their work, respondents replied with a wide variety of topics (480 responses from 145 people).

Answers typically focused on the application rather than specific computational tools, or workflows. For example: “I need to learn how to analyse scRNAseq data” or “I need to learn

Many omics data types and a variety of biological applications were mentioned within the responses categorised under “Analysis of omics data”. Genomics data was the most commonly mentioned with multiple methods and applications named, for example, analysis

of sequencing data (e.g. NGS, WGS) (32 responses from 28 individuals), and genome assembly and annotation (22 responses from 21 individuals). Other prominent subcategories include transcriptomics (especially analysis of RNAseq data) (68 responses from 54 individuals), and Single Cell Analysis and Spatial omics (58 responses from 42 individuals).

The training needs categorised under Programming and computational skills reflect the competencies required by computational biologists to develop and maintain reproducible bioinformatics methods⁸. The most popular subcategories under “Programming and computational skills” were:

- Workflow management and pipelines (e.g. Nextflow and Snakemake) (34 responses from 29 individuals)
- Programming languages (e.g. R and Python) (24 responses from 22 individuals)
- Machine Learning and Deep Learning (22 responses from 20 people)
- Containerisation (14 responses from 12 individuals)

Of note, machine learning was an emerging need in our 2021 survey and it is no surprise to see that it continued to be a popular topic in 2023. This is in keeping with growing interest in AI/ML and known needs within the life science community to promote AI/ML literacy and to develop skills to leverage these methods^{9,10}.

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Figure 9: Visual representation of mapping of free text responses to the prompt “I need to learn how to...”. The total number of responses and number of individuals responding (in brackets) are provided beside each category.

Summary, reflections and concluding remarks

This survey provides a snapshot of bioinformatics training needs in the life science community in Australia in late 2023.

In this iteration of the survey we encouraged respondents to list their training needs in response to the prompt “I need to learn how to...”. This allowed us to capture a greater variety of responses compared with previous surveys. It also offered the unexpected (but perhaps not surprising) insight that for trainees the focus is on what they need to achieve rather than how they need to achieve it. This highlights the important role for subject matter experts and trainers in role modelling best practices and selecting methods that are appropriate for the audience.

Overall, the outcomes are similar to those we observed in 2021 with continued need for training on analysis of omics data, workflow management and a variety of tools, platforms and computational methods. New topics identified in our 2021 survey (e.g. Single Cell RNAseq and Machine learning) continue to be popular in 2023 and we expect that interest in these will continue to grow with increased use of these methods. Spatial omics was an emerging topic in the results of the 2023 survey reflecting the growing popularity of this method¹¹.

Societal shifts to favour blended modes of working are reflected in our results with live-online training equally as popular as live in-person training³. Importantly, respondents indicated a desire for live training supported by self-paced materials. Combining these formats promotes continual catalytic learning that enhances skills development and should be taken into consideration when designing bioinformatics training¹².

The information gathered in this survey provides a starting point for conversations about the bioinformatics training needs of the Australian life science community. It is being used by the National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative, Australian BioCommons and partners to inform the development of our training programs. Future surveys will enable us to track changes in training needs over time and respond to shifts in demand and scientific thinking.

Contributors

This survey was developed, run and analysed by the [National Bioinformatics Training Cooperative](#), convened by Australian BioCommons.

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Supplementary files

- Questions asked in the survey (PDF): SurveyQuestions.pdf
- All responses to the survey (CSV): All_responses.csv
- Final categorisation of training needs (CSV): Categorised_responses_training_needs.csv
- Table of responses per organisation (CSV): Responses_per_organisation.csv

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